

DETERMINATION OF LIGHTNING INDUCED EFFECTS IN AERONAUTIC SYSTEMS BY ANALYTICAL FORMULATION

Y. Corredores¹, L. Pniak¹, P-E Levy², S. Lallechere¹, F. de Daran¹

⁽¹⁾ Safran Tech, Rue des jeunes Bois, 78117 Châteaufort, France,

⁽²⁾ ENS Paris Saclay, 4 avenue des sciences, 91190 Gif-sur-Yvette, France

{yonathan.corredores, lucas.pniak, francois.de-daran, sebastien.lallechere}@safrangroup.com,

pierre-etienne.levy@ens-paris-saclay.fr

Keywords: S-PEEC, Analytical, Lightning, Aeronautic.

1. ABSTRACT

This paper deals with an original approach relying on the Partial Element Equivalent Circuit (PEEC) method through an analytic integration of PEEC equations. This work especially focuses on the implementation of a surface formalism (here called Surface PEEC, S-PEEC) including both the theoretical principles and various simulations with canonical structures subject to lightning strike. The very good agreement between S-PEEC and 3-D full-wave tools (here CST and Flux commercial software) validates the given methodology.

2. INTRODUCTION

When a lightning strike reaches aircrafts, we can observe two different effects: (i) mechanical and thermal stresses in the structure (direct effects); (ii) undesired currents and voltages on harness and equipment induced by lightning current circulating on the structure (indirect effects). The increase in the number of electric systems in aircrafts makes it critical to predict and evaluate indirect effects to ensure safety and system availability.

In order to specify the system protections, lightning tests would be the most relevant method to estimate undesired currents and voltages. Nevertheless, experimental tests are expensive, time consuming and require the exact system topology to be representative. In this framework, numerical simulations can also predict indirect effects. In order to perform them, several software based on diverse methods (e.g., Finite Difference in Time Domain (FDTD), Method of Moment (MoM), Finite Element (FE), Partial Element Equivalent Circuit (PEEC) are used [1, 2, 3]. For large and complex structures, mesh must be small enough compared to the wavelength (100 MHz, ~3 m) leading to a noticeable simulation time and computing resources. Most of the time, some design choices (e.g., harness routing and ground connections) are achieved at system level without been optimized by simulation. Due to their computing costs (mostly time and memory here); simulations are usually scheduled at the end of the system design, just before certification phase. Therefore, Safran Tech investigates fast and accurate simulation tools to help designers take relevant decisions at system level at early stage in the design process.

PEEC method is particularly interesting for the first part of a system definition. It readily provides an equivalent electric circuit representing the structure, harness and equipment. Considering the lightning wavelength and dimensions of the structure, a surface formulation of the PEEC method is

preferred. The definition of the equivalent electrical circuit requires the calculation of the ($N \times N$) impedance matrix of the modeled structure (assuming N unknown equivalent electrical parameters). Conventional PEEC methods solves equation numerically [4], meaning the following equation (1) is resolved through numerical approaches. For a few dozen of surfaces, the calculation is fast enough (~ ms) but an increase in the surface number N leads to an exponential increase in simulation time and computing resources [5], wasting PEEC advantages over the other methods.

First, this paper will present the progress for fast and strict simulations with an original implementation of the PEEC method (namely Surface PEEC, S-PEEC). Further, we will demonstrate the ability of the proposed methodology to assess the current distribution and coupling effects in canonical structures subject to a lightning strike.

3. ANALYTIC S-PEEC FORMULATION

The calculation of the magnetic coupling in a system can be obtained by the well-known PEEC method [6]. The calculation of the electromagnetic field is achieved through the use of the potential vector \vec{A} (1):

$$\vec{A}(\vec{r}') = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \iiint_{V_1} \frac{\vec{I}_1}{|\vec{r}' - \vec{r}^j|} dV_1 \quad (1)$$

with μ_0 , the magnetic permeability of vacuum, \vec{I}_1 , the current volume density, V_1 , the volume of the conductor, \vec{r}^j , the position of the conductor and \vec{r}' , the point where the potential vector is calculated. The equation (1) allows an easier calculation of the partial mutual inductance as presented in (2).

$$M_{12} = \frac{1}{S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot |\vec{I}_1|} \iiint_{V_2} \vec{A}_1 \cdot d\vec{V}_2 \quad (2)$$

where, \vec{A}_1 is the potential vector associated to the conductor 1, V_2 is the volume associated to conductor 2, S_1 and S_2 are the transversal sections of conductor 1 and 2, respectively. By replacing equation (1) in equation (2), we get a general expression (3) to calculate partial mutual inductance between two conductors.

$$M_{ij} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi \cdot S_i \cdot S_j} \iiint_{V_i} \iiint_{V_j} \frac{1}{|\vec{r}' - \vec{r}^j|} d\vec{V}_i d\vec{V}_j \quad (3)$$

As can be seen, the calculation of the partial mutual inductances requires successive integrations of the distance function ($1/R$), between any point P in conductor 1 and any point M in conductor 2. The methods of the state of the art, for solving (3) analytically can be very complex or even not allow an analytical expression. For this reason, several authors [7, 8, 9] have presented methods to express these couplings but they are either simplified or they have opted for a numerical resolution. For example, authors in [7] simplifies the problem by forcing the surfaces to be in the Cartesian planes (xoy , yoz , $xoz\dots$), leading to a limitation in the geometric description.

In order to facilitate the solution of equation (3), we have developed a methodology considering thin parallelepiped meshing of conductors. For example, for two conductors randomly arranged in a reference coordinate system O_0 (see Fig. 1); the next steps are necessary to calculate the partial mutual inductance.

Fig. 1. Two conductors arranged randomly in a reference frame O_0

- First, we will create a Cartesian coordinate system A_1 , defined by the orthonormal basis $(\vec{e}_{x_1}, \vec{e}_{y_1}, \vec{e}_{z_1})$. A_1 coincides with the width, length and thickness of conductor 1. In the general case, A_1 does not coincide with the reference system O_0 .
- Second, we will create a Cartesian coordinate system A_2 defined by the orthonormal basis $(\vec{e}_{x_2}, \vec{e}_{y_2}, \vec{e}_{z_2})$. A_2 coincides with the width, length and thickness of conductor 2. In the general case, A_2 coincides neither with O_0 nor A_1 .
- Third, we let the coordinates (x_1, y_1, z_1) define any location of point P , on the conductor 1 and the coordinates (x_2, y_2, z_2) define any location of point M , on the conductor 2. The subscripts one and two indicate that the coordinates are with respect to the coordinate system A_1 and A_2 , respectively.
- Fourth, the equation (4) expresses the distance between any point P and the origin of its coordinate system A_1 and the equation (5) expresses the distance between any point M and the origin of its coordinate system A_2 .

$$\vec{A_1P} = x_1 \vec{e}_{x_1} + y_1 \vec{e}_{y_1} + z_1 \vec{e}_{z_1} \quad (4)$$

$$\vec{A_2M} = x_2 \vec{e}_{x_2} + y_2 \vec{e}_{y_2} + z_2 \vec{e}_{z_2} \quad (5)$$

- Fifth, the distance between the coordinate system A_1 and A_2 is constant (6).

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{A_1A_2} &= a_1 \vec{e}_{x_1} + b_1 \vec{e}_{y_1} + c_1 \vec{e}_{z_1} \\ &= a_2 \vec{e}_{x_2} + b_2 \vec{e}_{y_2} + c_2 \vec{e}_{z_2} \\ &= \text{constant} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Where, a_1, b_1, c_1 and a_2, b_2, c_2 define the position from A_1 and A_2 , respectively, to the reference coordinate system O_0 .

- Sixth, the distance (R) between any point P (conductor 1) and any point M (conductor 2) is defined in any coordinate system (A_1, A_2) as:

$$\begin{aligned} |\vec{R}| &= |\vec{PM}| = \sqrt{\Delta x_1^2 + \Delta y_1^2 + \Delta z_1^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\Delta x_2^2 + \Delta y_2^2 + \Delta z_2^2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

With,

$$\Delta x_1 = i_2 \cdot \Delta x_2 + j_2 \cdot \Delta y_2 + k_2 \cdot \Delta z_2 \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta y_1 = \kappa_2 \cdot \Delta x_2 + \lambda_2 \cdot \Delta y_2 + \mu_2 \cdot \Delta z_2 \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta z_1 = \alpha_2 \cdot \Delta x_2 + \beta_2 \cdot \Delta y_2 + \gamma_2 \cdot \Delta z_2 \quad (10)$$

And,

$$\Delta x_2 = i_1 \cdot \Delta x_1 + j_1 \cdot \Delta y_1 + k_1 \cdot \Delta z_1 \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta y_2 = \alpha_1 \cdot \Delta x_1 + \beta_1 \cdot \Delta y_1 + \gamma_1 \cdot \Delta z_1 \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta z_2 = \kappa_1 \cdot \Delta x_1 + \lambda_1 \cdot \Delta y_1 + \mu_1 \cdot \Delta z_1 \quad (13)$$

The constants $a_1, b_1, c_1, a_2, b_2, c_2, i_1, j_1, k_1, i_2, j_2, k_2, \kappa_1, \lambda_1, \mu_1, \kappa_2, \lambda_2, \mu_2, \alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1, \alpha_2, \beta_2, \gamma_2$ are deduced from projections of geometric frame A_1 over A_2 or vice versa.

For reasons of simplicity and because we are interested in the lightning phenomenon (low frequency < 10 MHz), we will apply the methodology for the surface definition of the PEEC method. The extended form of equation (3) in reference A_1 is equation (14).

$$\begin{aligned} M_{ij} &= \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi \cdot S_1 \cdot S_2} \cdot \\ &\int_{\Delta y_2} \int_{\Delta z_2} \int_{\Delta y_1} \int_{\Delta z_1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Delta x_1^2 + \Delta y_1^2 + \Delta z_1^2}} d\Delta z_1 d\Delta y_1 d\Delta z_2 d\Delta y_2 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Note that affine changes of variable have been made to simplify the writing and calculation of integrals: $y_1 \mapsto \Delta y_1$, $z_1 \mapsto \Delta z_1$, $y_2 \mapsto \Delta y_2$ and $z_2 \mapsto \Delta z_2$. The result of first integration respect to $d\Delta z_1$ (calculated by integration by parts) is presented in equation (15).

$$\begin{aligned} M_{ij} &= \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi \cdot S_1 \cdot S_2} \\ &\cdot \left[\int_{\Delta y_2} \int_{\Delta z_2} \int_{\Delta y_1} -\ln \frac{\Delta z_1 + \sqrt{\Delta x_1^2 + \Delta y_1^2 + \Delta z_1^2}}{\sqrt{\Delta x_1^2 + \Delta y_1^2}} d\Delta y_1 d\Delta y_2 d\Delta z_2 \right]_{\Delta z_1} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The result of second integration respect to $d\Delta y_1$ (also calculated by integration by parts) is presented in equation (16).

$$M_{ij} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi \cdot S_1 \cdot S_2} \cdot \quad (16)$$

$$\left[\int_{\Delta y_2} \int_{\Delta z_2} \left(\begin{array}{l} +\Delta y_1 \cdot \ln \frac{\Delta z_1 + \sqrt{\Delta x_1^2 + \Delta y_1^2 + \Delta z_1^2}}{\sqrt{\Delta x_1^2 + \Delta y_1^2}} \\ +\Delta z_1 \cdot \ln \frac{\Delta y_1 + \sqrt{\Delta x_1^2 + \Delta y_1^2 + \Delta z_1^2}}{\sqrt{\Delta x_1^2 + \Delta y_1^2}} \\ -\Delta x_1 \cdot \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\Delta y_1 \cdot \Delta z_1}{\Delta x_1 + \sqrt{\Delta x_1^2 + \Delta y_1^2 + \Delta z_1^2}} \right) \end{array} \right) d\Delta z_2 d\Delta y_2 \right]_{\Delta y_1, \Delta z_1}$$

At this stage of the calculation, the definition of the two additional coordinate systems A_1 and A_2 takes on its full meaning and makes possible the calculation of the last two integrals (along $d\Delta z_2$ and $d\Delta y_2$). Thanks to the equations (8) to (10), we can rewrite equation (16) as (17):

$$M_{ij} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi \cdot S_1 \cdot S_2} \cdot \left[\int_{\Delta y_2} \int_{\Delta z_2} \left(\begin{array}{l} +(\kappa_2 \Delta x_2 + \lambda_2 \Delta y_2 + \mu_2 \Delta z_2) \cdot \ln \frac{(\alpha_2 \Delta x_2 + \beta_2 \Delta y_2 + \gamma_2 \Delta z_2) + \sqrt{\Delta x_2^2 + \Delta y_2^2 + \Delta z_2^2}}{\sqrt{\Delta x_2^2 + \Delta y_2^2 + \Delta z_2^2} - (\alpha_2 \Delta x_2 + \beta_2 \Delta y_2 + \gamma_2 \Delta z_2)^2} \\ +(\alpha_2 \Delta x_2 + \beta_2 \Delta y_2 + \gamma_2 \Delta z_2) \cdot \ln \frac{(\kappa_2 \Delta x_2 + \lambda_2 \Delta y_2 + \mu_2 \Delta z_2) + \sqrt{\Delta x_2^2 + \Delta y_2^2 + \Delta z_2^2}}{\sqrt{\Delta x_2^2 + \Delta y_2^2 + \Delta z_2^2} - (\kappa_2 \Delta x_2 + \lambda_2 \Delta y_2 + \mu_2 \Delta z_2)^2} \\ -(i_2 \Delta x_2 + j_2 \Delta y_2 + k_2 \Delta z_2) \cdot \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{(\kappa_2 \Delta x_2 + \lambda_2 \Delta y_2 + \mu_2 \Delta z_2) \cdot (\alpha_2 \Delta x_2 + \beta_2 \Delta y_2 + \gamma_2 \Delta z_2)}{(i_2 \Delta x_2 + j_2 \Delta y_2 + k_2 \Delta z_2) + \sqrt{\Delta x_2^2 + \Delta y_2^2 + \Delta z_2^2}} \right) \end{array} \right) d\Delta z_2 d\Delta y_2 \right]_{\Delta y_1, \Delta z_1} \quad (17)$$

Even if the integral seems more complex, its primitive are direct (third and fourth integrations are calculated by integration by parts). Due to space limitation, the complete formulation will not be given in this paper. Despite all, the calculation of the partial mutual inductance matrix will rely on the latter expressions.

4. CANONICAL STRUCTURES

4.1 Square Coils

The developed analytical S-PEEC formulation are validated with a simple geometry of two square coils (Fig. 2). The self-inductance (L) and the mutual inductance (M) are calculated. In order to have a point of comparison, two commercial software calculate also L and M : Altair Flux and CST STUDIO using a numerical volume PEEC and FDTD formulations, respectively.

Fig. 2. Geometry of two square coils placed randomly in space (left) Safran S-PEEC, (center) Altair Flux PEEC and (right) CST FDTD

For this example, five parallelepipeds placed in the XY plane define the first square coil. Five others parallelepiped placed randomly in the space define the second coil. Table 1 presents the four Cartesian coordinates completely defining each parallelepiped as depicted in Fig. 2. Coils thickness is 2 mm and conductivity $\sigma = 5.96e7$ S/m (aluminum).

Table 1. Coordinates of the parallelepipeds defining the coils (mm)

	x_1, y_1, z_1	x_2, y_2, z_2	x_3, y_3, z_3	x_4, y_4, z_4
1	50, 0, 0	50, 50, 0	150, 50, 0	150, 0, 0
2	0, 50, 0	50, 50, 0	50, 550, 0	0, 550, 0
3	50, 600, 0	50, 550, 0	360, 550, 0	360, 600, 0
4	410, 50, 0	360, 50, 0	360, 550, 0	410, 550, 0
5	160, 0, 0	160, 50, 0	360, 50, 0	360, 0, 0
6	113, 25, 392	75, 0, 370	25, 0, 457	62.5, 25, 478
7	37.5, 25, 522	62.5, 25, 478	438, 275, 695	413, 275, 738
8	593, 275, 426	630, 300, 448	475, 300, 717	438, 275, 695
9	243, 25, 167	218, 25, 210	593, 275, 426	618, 275, 380
10	218, 25, 210	180, 0, 188	80, 0, 361	118, 25, 383

In a frequency range between 10 Hz and 100 MHz, 1000 frequency points are calculated. PEEC codes (Safran and Flux) have taken less than 1 second, compared to CST software whose simulation has lasted 1m36s. We can observe in Fig. 3 (left) the inductance value 918 nH, 946 nH and 963 nH calculated by S-PEEC, Flux and CST, respectively. Moreover, in Fig. 3 (right) we can see the mutual inductance values 30.5 nH, 25 nH and 32 nH calculated by S-PEEC, Flux and CST, respectively. Which means, there is less than 5%-difference in the values of L and M , respectively between S-PEEC and CST formulations.

Fig. 3. Self-inductance and mutual inductance of two square coils obtained by three different software

Therefore, the above results validate the accuracy of the analytical S-PEEC formulation developed at Safran Tech. In contrast, this example does not allow realizing the gain in calculation time of the proposed formulation. Next section presents a structure to compare calculation time.

4.2 Solid of Revolution

To realize the gain in calculation time of the proposed PEEC formulation, a solid of revolution is taken as example. As mentioned, the surface expression (S-PEEC) is used due to the nature of the system under consideration (thin structures), the current distribution is mostly governed by 1D or 2D paths (here without 3D volumetric considerations). The structure consists in a copper cylindrical form $L 6 \text{ m} \times W 6 \text{ m} \times D 1.5 \text{ m}$ (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Copper cylindrical form used as canonical structure

This structure was chosen for its revolution symmetry, which characterizes most of aeronautical systems (nacelles, engines, fuselage...).

4.3 Mesh of the Structure

A first mesh is necessary to represent the structure by planar surfaces. We fit the structure with 300 trapezoidal planar surfaces each with $\sim 12 \text{ cm}$ side (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Trapezoidal mesh of the canonical structure defined by 300 planar surfaces

Actually, the developed S-PEEC method only takes into account rectangular surfaces; for this reason a second mesh must be built based on the first one (Fig. 6). Recent works [4, 9] will allow the implementation of non-orthogonal mesh. The Fig. 6 shows the 1200 (4×300) elementary cells representing the rectangular mesh of the solid of revolution.

Fig. 6. Rectangular mesh of the canonical structure defined by 1200 planar surfaces

As we can see, there is a factor 4 in the second mesh respect to the first. Actually, the equivalent circuit of an elementary cell (Fig. 7) is defined by 4 inductances and 4 resistances; each depends on the length and width of the cell, in general case they are different at least that the cell is a square. The reason for splitting the elementary cell in four distinct elements (resistance/inductance) relies on facilitating the circuit analysis as developed in subsection 4.5.

Fig. 7. Elementary cell mesh and its representation in the circuit model by 4 inductance and 4 resistances

4.4 Calculation RLM

The S-PEEC formulation has been implemented through Matlab framework to calculate the partial Resistances, Inductances and Mutual inductances (RLM) of the rectangular mesh (Fig. 6). The hardware characteristics of the used PC are Intel R Xenon Gold 6134 ($\times 2$), 3.20 GHz and 32 GB RAM. The matrix calculation (LRM) lasts ~ 325 secs (a RAM optimization could be achieved; actually the global matrix 1200×1200 was split through 9 parts to avoid RAM memory issues).

4.5 Circuit Analysis

The circuit analysis relies on graph theory principles [10]. Actually, this analysis is very practical in term of speed of calculation compared to a nodal analysis as SPICE; especially for structures like those studied here which presents hundreds of mutual inductances (Fig. 8). The analysis needs four steps:

Fig. 8. Equivalent circuit of four elementary meshes. The small close path input/output (green) and an elementary close path (red)

First, we define the number of edges ($N_{edges} = 4 \times N$) from the initial number of elements N , the number of nodes $N_{nodes} = ((4 \times N) - 1)$ and the number of networks ($N_{networks} = 1$).

Second, we find the shortest close paths in the circuit N_{mesh} (equation 18) and the input/output path. For this, the *Dijkstra* algorithm [11] is used (Fig. 8).

Third, the calculation of the connectivity matrix (C); this matrix makes the link between the edges matrix and the mesh matrix.

$$N_{mesh} = N_{edges} - N_{nodes} + N_{network} \quad (18)$$

Fourth, S-PEEC provides the impedance matrix (Z); the E -vector injection is achieved through an equivalent voltage source (it is calculated to simulate a current injection waveform A relying on graph theory [10] and lightning time and/or frequency source patterns), and the equation (19) is solved in time domain (frequency domain resolution available, data not shown here). The circuit integration for 100 μ s- duration takes \sim 280 sec, (120 sec is devoted to the mesh search algorithm).

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ \dots \\ I_{1200} \\ I_{in} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_1 & Z_{1_2} & \dots & Z_{1_{1200}} \\ Z_{2_1} & Z_2 & \dots & Z_{2_{1200}} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ Z_{1200_1} & Z_{1200_2} & \dots & Z_{1200} \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} * \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \dots \\ E_{in} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

The S-PEEC total time calculation is \sim 980 sec (16 min, respectively \sim 600 sec for impedance matrix and \sim 380 sec for circuit analysis) much lower than CST simulation time that requires more than 8000 sec (\sim 2h). It is to be noticed that S-PEEC requires only one impedance matrix calculation (at first), meaning only the circuit analysis should be updated in case of changes with input/output locations. In the same circumstances, CST simulation needs a global calculation (\sim 2h). On the other hand, the commercial software Flux can only calculate in frequency domain, thus a straightforward comparison is not possible. To give an overview, Flux software takes 30 sec for one single frequency and a specific input/output (supplied-conductors option).

A time domain solution is preferable for lightning analysis then Flux results must be transformed using an Inverse Fourier Transform. If this enables calculation for only 100 frequency points, it has to be noted the needed simulation time reaches 3000 sec (\sim 50 min).

4.6 Results

Fig. 9 (left) depicts the current cartography obtained with the proposed method (S-PEEC, input lightning injection and output measurement given in Fig. 9 (left)); it is also calculated with CST commercial software, as pointed out in Fig. 9 (right).

Fig. 9. Lightning current across canonical structure (left) S-PEEC (right) CST STUDIO

The comparison of the results obtained from the current flowing on the canonical structure are in a very good agreement with respect to its propagation pattern.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has first presented a novel method to solve analytically PEEC integrals. The proposed method allows a faster calculation of impedance matrix for complex geometries and needs less computational resources. In a second time, the precision of the proposed method has been tested by calculating the inductance and mutual inductance of two square coils; the difference respect to commercial software is \sim 4%. Finally, a lightning waveform A has been injected to a complex structure and current levels have been calculated with S-PEEC method and compared with CST commercial software.

The presented S-PEEC method is currently tested in an aeronautical system (Nacelle, Fig. 10). The end goal is to know the lightning constrains in the electrical system (indirect-effects).

Fig. 10. Aeronautical system used to test S-PEEC analytical formulation (top) CAO structure, (bottom left) mesh of a simplified nacelle, (bottom right) simplified nacelle and the electric system

6. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Bandinelli, A. Mori, G. Galgani, D. Romano, G. Antonini, A.G. Dieudonné and M. Dunand, "A Surface PEEC Formulation for High-Fidelity Analysis of the Current Return Networks in Composite Aircrafts," in *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 57, no. 5, pp. 1027-1036, Oct. 2015.
- [2] P. Aguilera, C. Lair, F. Issac and B. Michielsen, "A reciprocity approach to the indirect effects of lightning impact on an aircraft engine," *2016 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility - EMC EUROPE, Wroclaw, 2016*, pp. 343-346.
- [3] J.-P. Parmantier et al., "Indirect Effects of Lightning on Aircraft and Rotorcraft," *Journal Aerospace-Lab, Lightning Hazards to Aircraft and Launchers, Issue 5*, pp.20-24, December 2012.
- [4] A. E. Ruehli, G. Antonini, J. Esch, J. Ekman, A. Mayo and A. Orlandi, "Nonorthogonal PEEC formulation for time- and frequency-domain EM and circuit modeling," in *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp. 167-176, May 2003.
- [5] H. Moussa, M. Abdi, F. Issac and D. Prost, "Lightning modelling: From 3D to circuit approach," *2012 ESA Workshop on Aerospace EMC, Venice*, pp. 1-5, 2012.
- [6] A. E. Ruehli, "Inductance Calculations in a Complex Integrated Circuit Environment," in *IBM Journal of Research and Development*, vol. 16, Issue 5, pp. 470 - 481, Sept. 1972.
- [7] D. Romano, G. Antonini, L. Lombardi, U. Grossner and I. Kovačević-Badstübner, "Analytical Formulas for the Computation of the Electric Field in the Partial Element Equivalent Circuit Method With Conductive, Dielectric, and Magnetic Media," in *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 55, no. 10, pp. 1-13, Oct. 2019.
- [8] I. Kovacevic-Badstuebner, D. Romano, G. Antonini, L. Lombardi and U. Grossner, "Full-Wave Computation of the Electric Field in the

Partial Element Equivalent Circuit Method Using Taylor Series Expansion of the Retarded Green's Function," in IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques, vol. 68, no. 8, pp. 3242-3254, Aug. 2020.

- [9] G. Antonini, A. Orlandi and A. E. Ruehli, "Analytical integration of quasi-static potential integrals on nonorthogonal coplanar quadrilaterals for the PEEC method," in *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 399-403, May 2002.
- [10] W.-K. Chen, *Graph Theory and Its Engineering Applications, Advanced Series in Electrical and Computer Engineering Vol. 5, chapter 2 Foundation of electrical theory*, 1997 by World Scientific Publishing Co. ISBN 981-02-1859-1
- [11] M. Enayattabar, A. Ebrahimnejad, H. Motameni, 'Dijkstra algorithm for shortest path problem under interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy environment', *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, 2019, vol. 5, no 2, p. 93-100.